

Notes

Magnetic and Spectral Studies on Os(IV)-Mercapto Propionic Acid Complex

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OSMIUM can assume different co-ordination numbers depending upon the oxidation states of the metal^{1,2}. In the present studies α -mercapto propionic acid ($\text{CH}_3\text{CHSHCOOH}$)³⁻⁷, hereafter abbreviated as α -MPA, has been found to form a stable complex with Os(IV) metal ions.

Preparation of the complex: 50 ml. of 0.1 M solution of OsO_4 were added to 200 ml equimolar solution of α -mpa in aqueous media. A light brown colour appeared, a maximum intensity was obtained at pH 10.5 by the addition of NaOH. The dark brown coloured complex was evaporated on water bath, and an oily layer was left behind. This oily layer was extracted with acetone and chloroform, brown coloured complex obtained, was washed with ethanol and dried in an oven at 70°. The compound decomposed at 200°. Limited solubility in cold water prevented cryoscopic and conductometric measurements. Yield 60%. Disodium di hydroxy-di-mercapto propionato osmiumate(IV), $\text{Na}_2[\text{Os}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{S})_2(\text{OH})_2]$, required C=18.56%, H=3.09% and S=16.50% and was found to have C=17.88%, H=2.82% and S=16.34%.

Magnetic measurements at room temperature were made on powder form of the complex employing Gouy's method. Mercury(II) tetrathiocyanato cobaltate(II) was used as calibrant.

Absorption spectra of the complex were recorded in water on Beckman DU spectrophotometer. The observed bands are discussed with their tentative assignments.

The I. R. spectra of the ligand and the complex were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 2350 spectrophotometer. The tentative assignment of I. R. peaks are discussed.

Discussion

Osmium (VIII), which is the starting material seems to have been reduced by the ligand in the alkaline medium to Osmium(IV). Os(IV) has a (t_{2g})⁴ configuration and hence two unpaired electrons. It would, therefore, be expected to exhibit a paramagnetism corresponding to two unpaired electrons. In the present case the magnetic moment value has been found 1.3 B. M.. The low magnetic moment value may be due to large spin-orbit coupling in octahedral complex of tetravalent Osmium, which is $\sim 2000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. In fact

many Osmium(IV) compounds have been found to exhibit a magnetic moment between 1.2-1.7 B. M. at room temperature⁸⁻¹⁰.

Octahedral stereochemistry is further supported by the absorption spectra which show three bands at 18,350 cm^{-1} , 21,010 cm^{-1} and 35,300 cm^{-1} . According to Ballhausen¹¹ the ground state for Os(IV) would be (ν)_g⁴ producing at τ_1 level. Other excited levels are τ_4 and τ_3 , τ_5 and τ_3 and τ_5 and τ_1 . According to Jorgensen¹² the band at 18,350 cm^{-1} can be assigned to involve the electronic transition $\tau_1 \rightarrow \tau^2$. In addition, a great many charge transfer bands have been observed in case of K_2OsCl_6 . On this basis the other two bands in the present complex may be considered to be considered to be due to charge transfer.

I.R. spectra of the complex show the disappearance of $\nu\text{S-H}$ frequency which is obtained at 2550 cm^{-1} in the ligand spectrum, indicating removal of the sulphhydryl hydrogen and formation of metal sulphur bond. This is further confirmed by the observed lowering in the position of the C-S stretching frequency from 740 cm^{-1} in the ligand to 710 cm^{-1} in the complex. Change of $\nu_{\text{asym. COO}}$ & $\nu_{\text{s,m COO}}$ of the carboxylic group in the complex as compared to that in the free ligand suggesting unidentate co-ordination of the carboxylic group. α -Mercapto propionic acid thus, appears to act as a binegative bidentate chelating agent.

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